

Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds. Part—V : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activities of N-Bridged Thiazole and Imidazole Derivatives

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Several benzoxazolo[3,2-b]thiazolium, benzothiazolo[3,2-b]thiazolium and pyridino[2,1-b]thiazolium perchlorate salts, thiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine and several of their higher homologues as hydrobromides (IV) and free bases, were synthesised by reacting the respective mercapto compounds with α -bromoketones. The free bases as well as the hydrobromides of 1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-b]imidazoles (VI) and 1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-b]imidazoles (VII) were synthesised by the reaction of aminoazoles with the same bromoketones. Besides these, the synthesis of a few reduced N-bridged thiazole compounds (V) prepared by reacting the mercapto compounds with dihaloalkanes has been described. The structures of these compounds have been confirmed from spectral and analytical data and their bactericidal and fungicidal potencies have been evaluated.

THE versatile use of thiazole and imidazole compounds possessing -N-C-S-, -N-C-N- grouping respectively as antitubercular¹ and anti-radiation² agents and their applications as anthelmintics³, nematocides⁴ and vulcanisation accelerators⁵ have stimulated considerable interest to explore the possible synthesis of new potential compounds in which the thiazole or imidazole ring is fused with another biologically active nucleus through nitrogen atom. In the present communication, the synthesis of three types of such N-bridged thiazole derivatives in which the thiazole ring is fused to another heterocyclic ring such as benzothiazole, benzoxazole, pyridine, reduced pyrimidine and its higher homologues, imidazoline, thiadiazole and oxadiazole has been reported.

The N-bridged compounds (III), isolated as perchlorate salts were obtained by reacting the sodium salt of the mercapto compounds with α -bromoketones. The ketosulphides (I), isolated as intermediates, were cyclised in the presence of conc H_2SO_4 . The uv spectrum of the ketosulphide (I; A=benzothiazolyl-2, R=phenyl) showed a broad band at 290 nm correspondingly to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition whereas its cyclised products (III) showed a bathochromic shift and the band appeared at 312 nm due to the extensive conjugation of the π bonds. Similarly the ir of the same ketosulphide gave a sharp carbonyl absorption at 1730 cm^{-1} which was absent in the cyclised product. The second type of N-bridged thiazolo compounds (IV), isolated as the hydrobromides, were prepared by reacting the cyclic thioureas with bromoketones by following the general procedure reported by Chadha *et al*^{6,7}. The free bases of the hydrobromide salts have also been isolated after neutralising the aqueous solution either with K_2CO_3 or

ammonia. The third type of fused thiazole derivatives (V) in which thiazole or thiazine moieties are partially saturated were synthesised by reacting the alkylhalides (1,2-dichloroethane, 1,3-dibromopropane and 1,4-dibromobutane) with a few cyclic thioureas.

Besides these, the N-bridged imidazole derivatives (VI and VII) in which the ring is fused with either 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl or 1,3,4-oxadiazolyl moiety have been synthesised by reacting the 2-amino-5-substituted thiadiazoles and oxadiazoles respectively with bromoketones.

Antimicrobial tests: The bactericidal activities of the compounds were evaluated by agar plate

technique using *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* and fungicidal tests were carried out using *A. niger* and *C. albican* in Sabouraud's broth medium.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra of the compounds were taken on KBr disc in Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

Benzoxazolyl-2-phenacyl sulphide (I; A=benzoxazolyl-2, R=C₆H₅): 2-Mercaptobenzoxazole (3 g; 0.02 mole) in methanol (70 ml) was taken in a 500 ml round bottomed flask provided with a mechanical stirrer. Metallic sodium (0.02 mole) was added to it portion wise. To the resulting clear solution phenacylbromide (2.0 g) was added in portions with stirring and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The needle-shaped crystals were filtered off, m.p. 115-116°, yield 2.0 g (70%). (Found : S, 12.90. C₁₅H₁₁O₂NS requires S, 12.89%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) : 276 ($\epsilon = 5 \times 10^4$); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 2845, 1750, 1690.

3-Phenylbenzoxazol[3,2-b]thiazolium perchlorate (III; A=benzoxazolyl-2, R=C₆H₅): The above ketosulphide (1.35 g) was dissolved in ice cold conc H₂SO₄ (12 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hr. The resulting solution was then poured cautiously to 300 ml of ice cold anhydrous ether and the mixture was kept in the refrigerator for 2 days. The ether layer was decanted off from an oil. The ether was evaporated at room temperature and the residue was dissolved in small quantity of water and filtered. The solution was treated with 35% HClO₄ (5 ml) and kept overnight during which the perchlorate salt precipitated out. It was filtered, washed several times with cold ether and dried in air, m.p. 202-3°, yield 62%. (Found : S, 8.85. C₁₈H₁₁NO₂SCI requires 9.10%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) : 307 ($\epsilon = 4 \times 10^4$); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 1685, 1206.

Benzo-thiazolyl-2-phenacyl sulphide (I; A=benzo-thiazolyl-2, R=C₆H₅): This was prepared as colourless needles by taking 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (0.42 g), metallic sodium (0.05 g) and phenacylbromide (0.5 g) in methanol (20 ml) by following the above procedure, m.p. 207°, yield 350 mg (50%). (Found : S, 22.18. C₁₅H₁₁NS₂O requires S, 22.45%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) : 290 ($\epsilon = 3.2 \times 10^4$); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 2910, 1750, 1685, 1305.

3-Phenylbenzothiazolo[3,2-b]thiazolium perchlorate (III; A=benzothiazolyl-2, R=C₆H₅): The above ketosulphide (0.28 g) was cyclised with ice cold conc H₂SO₄ (5 ml) and the product was isolated as perchlorate salt by following the general work up procedure, m.p. 221°, yield 50%. (Found : S, 17.19. C₁₈H₁₀O₄NS₂Cl requires S, 17.42%); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ (nm) : 310 ($\epsilon = 6 \times 10^4$); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ (cm⁻¹) : 1690, 1460, 1300.

Pyridyl-2-phenacyl sulphide (I; A=pyridyl-2, R=C₆H₅): This was prepared from 2-mercaptopyridine (1.1 g) and phenacylbromide (2.0 g) in methanol and metallic sodium (0.2 g) by following the general procedure as colourless needles, m.p. 107°, yield 1.4 g (65%). (Found : S, 13.97. C₁₅H₁₁NSO requires S, 13.84%).

3-Phenyl-pyridino[2,1-b]thiazolium perchlorate (III; A=pyridyl-2, R=C₆H₅): The above thio-ketone (1.15 g) was cyclised using conc H₂SO₄ and the product was isolated as the perchlorate salt, m.p. 207°(d). (Found : S, 14.02. C₁₅H₁₁NOS requires S, 13.97%).

3-Phenyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrothiazolo[3,2-a]pyrimidine hydrobromide (IV; N=3, R=C₆H₅): A mixture of 2-mercapto-3,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine (1.16 g; 0.01 mole) and phenacylbromide (2 g) in ethanol (25 ml) was heated under reflux on a water bath for 12 hr. Dirty white crystals separated after concentrating the solution. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol as white crystals, m.p. 258°, yield 2.1 g (70%). (Found : S, 10.75; Br, 26.62. C₁₅H₁₅N₂SBr requires S, 10.77; Br, 26.93%).

The free base was obtained after neutralising the aqueous solution with K₂CO₃ in almost quantitative yield, m.p. 139°. (Found : S, 14.43. C₁₅H₁₅N₂S requires S, 14.81%).

3-Phenyl-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrothiazolo[3,2-a](1,3)diazepine hydrobromide (IV; n=4, R=C₆H₅): It was prepared by taking 2-mercaptodiazepine (1.30 g; 0.01 mole) and phenacylbromide (2 g) in ethanol (20 ml) following the general work up procedure mentioned earlier, m.p. 246°, yield 1.2 g (45%). (Found : S, 11.08. C₁₅H₁₅N₂SBr requires S, 10.29%).

The free base was obtained as crystalline needles after neutralisation with aqueous ammonia, m.p. 111°. (Found : S, 13.63. C₁₈H₁₄N₂SBr requires S, 13.91%).

2,3,5,6-Tetrahydrothiazolo[3,2-a]imidazole hydrochloride (V; n=m=2): Ethylene thiourea (0.4 g) and 1,2-dichloroethane (0.4 g) in absolute alcohol (20 ml) were refluxed on a water bath for 6 hr. After cooling, fine crystals of thiazoloimidazole hydrochloride separated, m.p. 196°, yield 0.5 g (63%). (Found : S, 19.04. C₅H₉N₂SCI requires S, 19.45%).

The other compounds prepared by the above procedure are V (n=3, m=2, X=Cl), m.p. 206°. (Found : S, 17.86. C₈H₁₁N₂SCI requires S, 18.13%); V (n=4, m=2, X=Cl), m.p. 217°. (Found : S, 17.54. C₇H₁₃N₂SCI requires S, 17.68%); V (n=2, m=4, X=Br), m.p. 208(d). (Found : S, 13.44. C₇H₁₃H₂SBr requires S, 13.67%); V (n=m=3, X=Br), m.p. 214°. (Found : S, 13.51. C₇H₁₃N₂SBr requires S, 13.67%).

2,5-Diphenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolo[3,2-b]imidazole hydrobromide (VII; X=R=C₆H₅): A mixture of 2-amino-5-phenyl oxadiazole (0.16 g) and phenacylbromide (0.2 g) in alcohol (15 ml) was heated under reflux on a water bath for 6 hr. The colourless solid separated after cooling was filtered,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND TEST RESULTS OF PERCHLORATE SALTS (III)

A	R	m.p. °C	%S Found (Calcd.)	SA	BS	CA*	AN*
Benzoxazolyl-2	Phenyl	—	—	+	+	50	50
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	223	8.15 (8.29)	+	2+	50	50
—do—	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	246	8.21 (8.88)	+	+	—	—
—do—	Thienyl-2	214	18.61 (18.74)	2+	+	100	100
—do—	Furyl-2	197	9.70 (9.83)	+	+	—	—
Benzothiazolyl-2	Phenyl	—	—	2+	2+	50	50
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	226	15.65 (15.92)	2+	2+	100	100
—do—	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	218	16.06 (16.10)	+	—	—	—
—do—	Thienyl-2	205	26.73 (26.85)	2+	+	—	100
—do—	Furyl-2	187	9.25 (9.37)	+	—	—	—
Pyridyl-2	Phenyl	—	—	+	—	—	—
—do—	Thienyl-2	176	20.00 (20.15)	+	+	—	100
—do—	Furyl-2	144	10.29 (10.61)	—	—	—	—

SA = *S. aureus*; BS = *B. subtilis*; CA = *C. albican*; AN = *A. niger*; + = zone size 6-8 mm; 2+ = zone size 9-14 mm; — = inactive.
* The number indicates minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/ml.

TABLE 2

n	R	Hydrobromide (IV)						Free base	
		m.p. °C	%Br Found (Calcd.)	SA	BS	CA*	AN*	m.p. °C	%S Found (Calcd.)
3	Phenyl	—	—	—	+	100	—	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	—	+	—	—	—	150	12.42 (12.74)
	Thienyl-2	286	26.15 (26.40)	+	2+	50	50	144	28.56 (28.82)
	Furyl-2	235	27.64 (27.87)	+	+	—	—	123	15.34 (15.53)
4	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	250	—	+	—	—	—	165	11.70 (11.93)
	Phenyl	246	—	+	+	100	—	—	11.78
	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	213	—	+	2+	100	—	120	(12.07)
	Thienyl-2	176	25.16 (25.28)	2+	—	—	100	164	27.16 (27.11)
	Furyl-2	189	26.90 (26.57)	+	—	—	—	150	—
5	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	193	—	—	—	—	—	129	11.25 (11.38)
	Phenyl	213	22.24 (24.61)	+	—	—	—	130	13.10 (13.11)
6	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	242	—	+	+	—	—	146	12.33 (12.35)
	Phenyl	209	24.46 (24.31)	+	—	—	—	117	12.29 (12.40)
7	Phenyl	200	23.10 (23.32)	+	+	—	—	106	—
8	Phenyl	207	22.24 (22.40)	+	+	—	—	111	11.12 (11.18)

SA = *S. aureus*; BS = *B. subtilis*; CA = *C. albican*; AN = *A. niger*; + = zone size 6-8 mm; 2+ = zone size 9-14 mm; — = inactive.
* The number indicates minimum inhibitory concentration in µg/ml.

washed with ether and dried, m.p. 226°, yield 150 mg (70%). (Found: Br, 23.18. C₁₆H₁₃N₅OBr requires Br, 23.32%).

The above hydrobromide was dissolved in water and neutralised by conc NH₄OH during which the free base separated in quantitative yield. It was

TABLE—3

X	R	Hydrobromide (VI)						Free base		
		m.p. °C	%Br Found (Calcd.)	SA	BS	CA**	AN**	m.p. °C	%S Found (Calcd.)	BS
H	Phenyl	235	28.48 (28.27)	2+	—	—	—	198	15.52 (15.76)	+
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	238	—	2+	—	—	—	193	13.45 (13.53)	—
Phenyl	Phenyl	254	22.72 (22.83)	—	—	100	—	192	11.32 (11.52)	—
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	227	—	—	+	—	—	172	—	—
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	218	20.48 (20.57)	2+	+	50	—	252	10.09 (10.23)	+
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	235	—	—	—	—	—	244	9.18 (9.22)	—
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	250	20.13 (20.33)	+	+	50	—	216	10.28 (10.39)	+
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	250	—	—	—	50	—	232	—	+
Hydrobromides (VII)										
Phenyl	Phenyl	225	23.18 (23.32)	+	+	—	—	208	15.76* (16.03)	+
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	222	—	—	—	—	—	198	—	—
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Phenyl	231	21.12 (21.19)	—	+	—	—	142	—	—
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	227	—	—	—	—	—	118	12.46* (12.65)	—
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	220	21.23 (21.45)	—	—	100	—	238	—	+
—do—	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	234	—	—	—	—	—	234	—	—

* indicates estimated sulphur percentage.

filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 208°. (Found : N, 15.78. $C_{10}H_8N_2O$ requires N, 16.03%).

3-Phenyl-(1,3,4-thiadiazolo)[3,2-*b*]imidazole hydrobromide (VI; $X=H$, $R=C_6H_5$): It was obtained as crystalline needles from 2-aminothiadiazole (0.5 g) and phenacylbromide (0.5 g) by following the above procedure, m.p. 235°, yield 400 mg (60%). (Found : Br, 28.30. $C_{10}H_8N_2Br$ requires Br, 28.27%).

The free base was obtained after neutralisation with ammonia as pale yellow solid, m.p. 198°, yield 58%. (Found : S, 15.52. $C_{10}H_8N_2S$ requires S, 15.76%).

The physical and analytical data and antimicrobial test results of various perchlorate salts, thiazolopyrimidine and their higher homologues and thiazolo thioxadiazolo derivatives have been presented in Tables 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

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